

A Data Flow Programming Framework for 6G-Enabled Internet of Things Applications

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Abstract—The adoption of 6G networks and related technologies by the Internet of Things (IoT) are expected to unlock novel advancements in several vertical industries, like Automotive and Robotics. One of the key enablers consists on expanding IoT applications across the entire Cloud-to-Things continuum. Thus, components can be (re)deployed anywhere and anytime according to the requirements at each point in time. As a consequence, application developers face new challenges to transparently interconnect these components, leading to patchwork designs that increase complexity, time to market, and development cost. This paper introduces a novel data flow programming framework, named Zenoh-Flow, that addresses the aforementioned challenges by providing unified abstractions, automated allocation, and deployment across the Cloud-to-Thing continuum. Zenoh-Flow additionally provides key functionalities for Automotive and Robotics, *e.g.*, deadlines, time-stamping and progress tracking. Preliminary results show that our proposed solution outperforms existing solutions, like ERDOS and ROS/ROS2. In particular, Zenoh-Flow achieves lower latency and higher throughput in synthetic benchmarks as well as a reduced computing and networking overhead in a real-world robotic scenario.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of Internet of Things (IoT) devices and the seamless integration of smart technologies is contributing for their integration into various vertical industries, like Automotive and Robotics. However, it has posed increased connectivity demands and requirements not only in terms of speed, latency, and capacity but also in terms of scalability, and efficient processing of data. The fifth-generation (5G) networks have played a pivotal role in supporting these requirements, which allied to the use of the entire cloud-to-things continuum, enables a vast network of interconnected devices that collect, exchange, and analyze data to enable intelligent decision-making. While 5G networks have undoubtedly paved the way for enhanced connectivity and enabled a multitude of IoT use cases, they still face certain constraints (*e.g.*, limited bandwidth, latency issues in high-density environments, scalability concerns, and secure communication). The sixth-generation (6G) networks promise to unlock a plethora of advancements to meet the evolving needs of IoT applications.

Nevertheless, developing and deploying 6G-powered IoT applications across the Cloud-to-Things continuum might still prove an inherently complex task using traditional methodologies, thus there is a pressing need for novel and innovative approaches to facilitate the development and management of applications throughout the entire Cloud-to-Things continuum. The seamless integration of diverse components, spanning

from the devices themselves up to the edge-based and cloud-based platforms, introduces challenges related to components connectivity, interoperability, and data management. Furthermore, the scale and heterogeneity of IoT ecosystems require holistic strategies to efficiently develop, deploy, and manage applications.

Nowadays, IoT applications widely adopt the *pipes-and-filters* [1], [2] programming paradigm, which consists of splitting a complex task into a well defined series of simple and independent processing steps called *filters*. While this pattern has proven to work well when the application runs on a single and isolated machine, forthcoming Automotive (AV) [3], [4] and Robotics scenarios [5], [6] are clearly showing that: (i) computations will need to span across multiple locations, from on-board vehicle and up to the edge or the cloud, and (ii) complex and dynamic data interactions need to be taken into account, as shown in Fig. 1. *Data Flow Programming (DFP)* [7] appears as a potential candidate, since it generalises *pipes-and-filters* by allowing applications to be represented as directed graph of components, called *operators*, as opposed to a linear pipeline [8]. In that respect, DFP is beneficial because it natively shifts the focus of developers towards the logic to be implemented by the operators rather than how those operators communicate. It is indeed the duty of the DFP framework to ensure that DFP operators effectively exchange information via a unified abstraction to streamline application development regardless of where the application is going to be deployed.

This work presents Zenoh-Flow: a novel DFP framework capable of operating over 6G-powered networks and natively designed for the *Cloud-to-Things continuum*. It provides a unified abstraction to application developers for handling the complexity of the underlying infrastructure. Zenoh-Flow goes beyond the state of the art by: (i) supporting a variety of connectivity protocols, coping with robust mechanisms for seamless interoperability and communication between diverse IoT devices; (ii) defining a unified abstraction and computing model accounting for the heterogeneity of the Cloud-to-Thing continuum; (iii) supporting a declarative definition of applications to easy development and deployment over the Cloud-to-Thing continuum; (iv) natively supporting real-time Automotive and Robotics applications, with features like deadlines, progress tracking, and time-stamping of data.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Sec. II briefly presents the motivational scenario for this work, followed by Sec. III where essential background concepts and

Fig. 1: Example of autonomous robotic application across the Cloud-to-Things continuum.

related work is described. Sec. IV presents our proposed solution - Zenoh-Flow, that is later evaluated in Sec. V. Finally Sec. VI concludes the paper and points at future research directions.

II. MOTIVATIONAL SCENARIO: AN AUTONOMOUS ROBOTICS APPLICATION

Fig.1 shows an example of a DFP-based application running on a 6G-powered network and deployed across the Cloud-to-Things continuum [9] with the goal of autonomously driving a mobile delivery robot. In this application, a robot is loaded with goods in a shopping mall and has to deliver them to customers' home. The lower part represents the physical infrastructure: field-deployed sensors and robots, computing facilities at the edge, and data centers in the Cloud. The upper part of the figure shows the components of the DFP-based Robotics application and their deployment locations in the infrastructure. The application modules are categorized into two types: (i) *input/output*, drawn in a triangle-shape, which are in charge of any interaction with the external world, and (ii) *operators*, drawn in a circle-shape, which take care of performing computations and producing new data. The application senses live data from the environment (1 and 2 in Fig. 1) and uses such data to detect obstacles (3), *e.g.*, other robots, cars, pedestrians, and panels (4), *e.g.*, speed limits, traffic lights. In order to be relevant, sensed data must be *recent*, *e.g.*, belonging to a small time window, few microseconds to seconds in the past. This information is used to generate a knowledge of the surroundings and it is used to (i) predict movement of moving obstacles, (ii) plan short-term goals, *e.g.*, steer left to avoid an obstacle, as well as (iii) plan long-

term goals, *e.g.*, the path between the shopping mall and the customer's house.

Computing and networking infrastructure can also provide services (11 and 12), for instance by providing contextual information from nearby robots. This data is also used to continuously refine the algorithms and as a consequence improve the performance of operators such as object detection and robot driving.

The different DFP operators are spread across the continuum [10] because of their different requirements:

(i) low-latency networking, required for all the modules that consumes real-time data, *e.g.*, (8), (3) and (4); (ii) access to context information, required to improve the decision making with relevant information from nearby robots, *e.g.*, (11), (12); (iii) access to powerful servers, required by heavy AI/ML based computations, *e.g.*, (13), (14);

Given such a complex application, it becomes paramount to facilitate its definition and development.

This includes considering different types of devices, networks, communication patterns, and runtimes, *e.g.*, bare metal, virtual machines, containers, that need to be supported.

III. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORKS

This section presents a brief overview of essential concepts as well as existing state-of-the-art on the target use cases.

A. Data Flow Programming

Data Flow Programming (DFP) [7] is a computational model that represents application as a directed graph (as presented in Fig. 2). Each node of the application graph, called *operator*, is a computational unit, while the directed arc between them

Fig. 2: Generic Data Flow Programming Graph

are unbounded FIFOs (First-In-First-Out) streams, called *links*. Links are named as *inputs* if they flow towards a node, or *outputs* if they depart from a node. Finally, the connection between a link and an operator is called a *port*. Ports are *typed* forcing a link to exist only between two ports of the same type [11]. Operators are executed concurrently and triggered following different strategies, e.g., all inputs need to be presents, or only a subset of them. The single execution of an operator is called *firing*. DFP allows developers to decompose a complex application into a set of simpler components and to arrange them in graphs whilst providing the necessary abstraction for communication. This allows developers to focus on the logic of each of those operators. Still, DFP doesn't define how to deal with real-time processing, deadlines, periodicity of computations, progress tracking, multiple locations and deployment options for the operators.

Kahn Processing Networks Kahn Processing Networks (KPN) [11] is a flavor of DPF, where links interconnecting operators represent not only the flow of information across the program but also the data dependency for each operator. In this sense, KPN firing strategy requires each operator to wait for all inputs to trigger the processing. However, KPN firing strategy poses limitations for more complex applications where processing over incomplete data is required. For example, the *perception* operator (5 in Fig.1) needs to produce some output as soon as one of its input is available.

Dataflow Process Networks Dataflow Process Networks (DPNs) [12] is another flavor of DPF, which differs from KPNs by adopting a different firing strategy. Namely, operators can fire whenever a subset of the inputs is available, allowing computations to be performed on partial data. However, the inability to have a local state poses some limitations for more complex application that may require to track history. For example, the *prediction* operator (6 in Fig.1), needs to store the last positions for each object in order to predict their next position.

B. ERDOS

ERDOS [13] is a data flow framework designed to support Automotive and Robotics applications. It provides a DFP flavor based on DPN, and additional logic to enforce certain mechanisms: progress tracking, time constraints, fault-tolerance, and scaling models. Its main objective is to be able to dynamically adapt to the workload and react to failures or time constraint violations. Application graphs are defined programmatically, and operators are statically connected via TCP/IP streams, thus allowing the application to span across different machines.

ERDOS's computation model does not support loops in the application graph, making it impossible to model feedback systems. Nevertheless, being based on TCP/IP connectivity, it requires location-awareness which limits mobility and makes deployment across an E2E infrastructure difficult. Furthermore, ERDOS does not provide any functionality for automated deployment of application graphs. Thus, developers need to deal with the complexity of deployment and network configuration across the Cloud-to-Thing continuum.

C. Robot Operating System (ROS)

ROS [14] is a robotic framework designed with the goal of increasing code reuse and speed-up robotics applications development. To some extent, it is implicitly using data flow, still limited in many of its concepts. The scope of ROS is to support single robot operations, requiring workstation-class computational capabilities onboard the robot, and symmetric and powerful network connectivity. ROS applications are arranged in a graph of peers, called *nodes*, that communicate with one another and compute over data. Those nodes leverage two different communication models provided by ROS: *Publish-Subscribe* and *Request-Reply*. Thus, the data flow graph is implicitly defined programmatically by the different publication/subscription pairs.

ROS2¹ builds on top of ROS' concepts and targets more complex systems. In particular, its goal is to support multi-robot operations, while requiring less computing and networking capabilities compared to ROS. The main difference between ROS and ROS2 is the replacement of the *rosmaster* by Data Distribution Service (DDS) [15], effectively introducing support for location transparency and deadlines, while keeping the same communication model.

Both ROS/ROS2 borrow concepts from DFP, like arranging the application in a graph, providing transparent communication between operators and typed links. Nevertheless, ROS and ROS2 do not provide an explicit computational model, applications are arranged as graphs, similar to DPF, but the graph definition is not explicit.

IV. DATA FLOW FRAMEWORK FOR THE CLOUD-TO-THING CONTINUUM

This section describes Zenoh-Flow: our proposed *decentralized data flow programming framework for the Cloud-to-Thing continuum* that leverages data-centric networking concepts [16].

Zenoh-Flow follows four main design goals, aligned with the view of next-generation IoT applications:

- 1) *Cloud-to-Thing native*: to deploy applications across the continuum, with automatic allocation of application operators.
- 2) *Declarative* to provide explicit application definition so as to enable the analysis and optimization of the application graph.
- 3) *Composition* to allow developers to reuse and combine operators.

¹<https://design.ros2.org/>

4) *Deterministic and time-aware*: to support time-stamping [17], deadlines, logging and replay.

These design goals primarily address the requirements coming from the AV and the Robotics domains, that are only partially supported by existing solutions.

A. Solution Overview

Zenoh-Flow takes its root in the DFP model: an application is represented as a directed graph of nodes, where a node is an independent part of the application and a directed link symbolizes a flow of data. Specifically, a link is an unbounded queue that connects the output of a node to the input of (at least) another one. The inputs and outputs are typed to guarantee compatibility.

However, Zenoh-Flow differs from traditional DFP on one major aspect: nodes can have side-effects. They can store a state and perform I/O operations. Allowing side-effects opens up several types of applications that would otherwise be impossible: AV pipelines need to keep a history to perform predictions, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning both rely on previous “knowledge”.

Based on their side-effects, we differentiate three types of nodes in an application: Sources, Sinks and Operators.

Sources and Sinks are where I/O operations with external components are performed, for instance, reading from a sensor, storing information in a database, or interacting with the motor of a robot. The difference between both is the direction in which these operations happen. A Source will perform the Inputs, feeding data to the Zenoh-Flow application, while a Sink will perform the Outputs, sending out the results.

An Operator does not perform I/O operations, nevertheless, it can keep an internal state.

Our motivation for this separation is to foster good practices. By separating the nodes that perform I/O operations from the core logic of the application, developers can isolate the unreliable parts, possibly moving them on different device to ensure optimal execution condition of the core logic.

One of the drawbacks of allowing nodes to have side-effects, is that determinism is no longer guaranteed. To mitigate this, Zenoh-Flow additionally forces all the data to be time-stamped by a Hybrid Logical Clock (HLC) [17]. The main advantage of an HLC is that, thanks to its timestamp scheme, data can be totally ordered. Having a total order means that it is possible to reproduce an execution — as long as the state of all the nodes is deterministic for an identical set of inputs and an identical order.

Lastly, Zenoh-Flow supports time-triggered execution where nodes can, for instance, be woken up periodically.

B. Architecture

Fig.3 depicts the functional architecture of our proposed solution:

- The *Runners* are in charge of executing the *user code*, abstracting data delivery. Each runner is in charge of a single operator.

Fig. 3: Functional architecture of the proposed framework. Yellow box highlights our original contribution

- A *DF instance* represents a DFP application running across the continuum. Each instance keeps track of its runtime information, and has access to the runners executing their operators.
- The *Dataflow runtime* is in charge of mapping applications to the infrastructure, managing the life-cycle of operators, and configuring the application’s *data plane*. A runtime runs on a single machine. All runtimes collaborate to provide a decentralized allocation.
- The *Control/Management plane* is in charge of the control and management communications across different runtimes in the continuum. It also stores information about the state of the infrastructure and any running application.
- The *Data plane* is in charge of moving the data between the operators and it is configured by the runtime.

To ensure optimal execution, the Control/Management plane has the following specific needs: (i) *data-centric and location-transparent communications* to facilitate discovery and fetching information across the whole continuum; (ii) *consistency* as each node of the infrastructure needs to have the same view to avoid unfeasible mapping and scheduling errors; (iii) *reliability* as losing control data leads to unstable and non-consistent systems; (iv) *Publish/Subscribe pattern* for timely notifications and push metrics; and, (v) *Request/Reply pattern* for Remote Procedure Call (RPC) across the infrastructure to query on-demand any up-to-date information.

Similarly, the Data plane is responsible for moving data between operators. It thus requires: (i) *location-transparent and data-centric communications*, facilitating the flow of data across the continuum where things can move; (ii) *Publish/Subscriber pattern*, as it maps well with the data pattern of data flow; and, (iii) *reliability* in order to ensure FIFO behaviour without any loss of data.

To better apprehend Zenoh-Flow we detail next a typical workflow to craft an application.

Fig. 4: Zenoh-Flow overview and End-to-End application deployment workflow

C. Solution Workflow

Application developers would start by defining and implementing the different nodes. The definition of a node consists in describing its ports, specific configuration, and the location of the implementation (shared library or script). The implementation follows Zenoh-Flow’s API.

The next step is to assemble the operators together in a *descriptor* file to create a full-fledged data flow graph. This first two steps are represented by step 1 in Fig. 4. The descriptor file acts as a contract that Zenoh-Flow *enforces*. It specifies how the nodes are interconnected, their requirements – *e.g.*, access to specific hardware resources – and how to deploy, automatically, the application across the Cloud-to-Thing continuum.

As listed in the design goals, operators can be reused between applications and even composed together. A motivation is to foster code reuse in order to increase development speed and, hopefully, facilitate collaboration.

The descriptor, along with the operators, are on-boarded into Zenoh-Flow (step 2 in Fig. 4) which stores them in a distributed registry (step 3 in Fig. 4).

Once an instantiation request is received, Zenoh-Flow creates the corresponding runtime graph by loading the operators from the distributed registry (step 4 in Fig. 4), and establishing the underlying communication between them (step 5 in Fig. 4) — all while strictly adhering to the descriptor.

D. Highlights

Summarizing, Zenoh-Flow introduces a wide range of functionalities that suit the next-generation 6G-powered IoT applications (*i.e.*, in Automotive and Robotics verticals), going beyond state of the art solutions: (i) application graphs are defined with a *declarative* approach, in contrast to ERDOS’s *programmatic* approach, and ROS/ROS2’s *implicit* approach; (ii) input data are timestamped (via HLC) and total ordering is

provided by augmenting the timestamps with unique IDs, while ERDOS, ROS and ROS2 provide data timestamping without guaranteeing total ordering; (iii) deployment of applications across the Cloud-to-Thing continuum is natively supported, instead of relying on external tools as with ERDOS and ROS/ROS2; (iv) explicit support for Automotive and Robotics functionalities such as loops and progress tracking, similarly to ERDOS but in contrast to ROS/ROS2 that leave the implementation of such functionalities to developers.

V. EVALUATION

In order to assess the impact of the proposed solution in IoT-related application scenarios (*i.e.* representative of automotive and robotics applications), a set of both synthetic and experimental tests were devised. For comparison, ERDOS [13], ROS [14], and ROS2² were selected as state-of-the-art frameworks due to their relevance and adoption in Automotive and Robotics applications.

A. Implementation

The implementation of Zenoh-Flow is open source³ as part of the Eclipse Zenoh project. Zenoh-Flow’s core is written in Rust, given its high-level of abstraction, performances, memory-safety, and portability. Rust’s memory-safety allows avoiding memory management errors, the most common type of errors when programming. Portability allows supporting different hardware architectures and operating systems composing the Cloud-to-Thing continuum, with a single code base.

Zenoh-Flow consists of 10505 lines of Rust code and it also provides C++ and Python APIs to enable porting existing applications and fast prototyping. Zenoh-Flow’s communications leverage Zenoh⁴, a data-centric communication

²<https://design.ros2.org/>

³<https://github.com/eclipse-zenoh/zenoh-flow>

⁴<https://zenoh.io>

Fig. 5: Tests application graphs, Latency and Throughput are both composed by a data source, an operator forwarding between its input and its output and a sink providing the results, while Robotic application has three sources of data, two computing operators and two sinks.

technology, as it addresses the requirements of Zenoh Flow (see Sec. IV-B). Zenoh has already proved to be an efficient data flow transport [18] as well as supporting robotics applications⁵.

While both Zenoh-Flow and ERDOS are written in Rust, their implementation differs quite substantially. Zenoh-Flow takes a pluggable approach on the communication technologies used for both Control and Data plane, while ERDOS is tied to TCP/IP. Another key differentiation is the multi-threading primitives used, Zenoh-Flow leverages green-threads, while ERDOS leverages OS threads. We selected green-threads since they better exploit the system resources thanks to a faster context switch compared to OS threads, and the capability to execute a large number of parallel computations.

Zenoh-Flow is executed as *daemons* running on different machines. Those daemons communicate via the control plane when it is time to instantiate a new application, configuring the data plane accordingly to the application graph enabling data to flow across the Continuum.

In ERDOS, applications are compiled as binaries and it is left to the users to leverage on third-party technologies for

deployment and data plane configuration.

Both ROS and ROS2 are written in C++, a common language in Robotics. Similarly to Zenoh-Flow, ROS2 comes with a pluggable approach for the data plane communication technology, thus different implementation of DDS can be used, while ROS is tied to its internal communication protocol. Similarly to ERDOS, ROS and ROS2 operators are compiled as binaries, delegating to the users the choice of a third-party tool for deployment and data plane configuration.

B. Synthetic Scenario

The goal of the synthetic tests is to assess the baseline performance of the proposed solution in terms of latency and throughput.

They have been performed on our testbed, composed of a server equipped with AMD Ryzen 5800X CPU, running at a fixed frequency of 4.0 GHz, 32GB of DDR4 3200MHz RAM, an SSD and 100GbE network card, running Ubuntu 20.04.3 LTS up-to-date at the time of the testing. The graphs representing the test applications are depicted in Fig. 5. For each applications all the operators were running on a single machine, and have been pinned to specific CPU cores, to exploit cache affinity.

Latency Tests: The goal of this test is to measure the E2E application latency for a simple pipeline. Fig.5a depicts the application tested that is composed of a source, injecting a timestamped data, an operator, forwarding data from its input to its output, and a sink, measuring the latency. All the operators run on the same machine, so that no clock synchronization is required. The messages are injected by the sources at different rates, to understand the behaviour of the framework with different loads.

Results: The results of the tests are illustrated in Fig. 6a with the median highlighted in red, along with Table I that provides a breakdown of the latency values, including the Coefficient of Variation (C_V). From this result, we can observe that the overall distribution of points is bimodal. As the messages rate increases, the system is jumping from one state to another. In particular, when the application frequency is close to the scheduler one, as it happens for 100 mgs/s, the two states are clearly visible. What happens in this case is that based on when the scheduling requests arrive to the scheduler they may not be interposed by a context switch, leading to effectively run one right after the other. Thus leveraging on temporal locality, leading to lower latency.

Overall, the results show that Zenoh-Flow outperforms ERDOS, delivering all messages in under 150 μ s. Although Zenoh-Flow presents a higher variance for lower message rates (mostly due to the scheduling of green threads), for higher message rates it achieves 3 times lower 99th percentile than ERDOS. For example, in ERDOS the value of outliers grows significantly to reach a maximum at 50 ms, which is one order of magnitude of the maximum latency experienced with Zenoh-Flow. Such difference comes from different assumptions and architectural choices. In particular, our proposed solutions is heavily based on green-threads while ERDOS is based on OS

⁵<https://discourse.ros.org/t/ros-2-tsc-meeting-minutes-2022-04-21/25293>

(a) Latency (lower is better)

(b) Throughput (higher is better)

Fig. 6: Comparison between ERDOS and Zenoh-Flow based on synthetic benchmarks.

threads. Green-threads context switch is usually less-costly than OS threads, leading therefore to a reduction in latency of $\sim 80\%$ for high message rates. Nevertheless, heavily relying on OS threads causes ERDOS to trash for high message rates, increasing even more the latency.

Framework	Min.	Median.	99th-tile	Max.	C_V
Zenoh-Flow					
Message rate					
1	15.0 μ s	23.5 μ s	108 μ s	133 μ s	0.72
10	6.00 μ s	24.5 μ s	131 μ s	134 μ s	0.71
100	2.00 μ s	16.0 μ s	123 μ s	131 μ s	0.91
1000	2.00 μ s	3.00 μ s	60 μ s	77.0 μ s	0.35
10000	1.00 μ s	3.00 μ s	40 μ s	103 μ s	0.24
100000	1.00 μ s	2.00 μ s	40 μ s	108 μ s	0.26
ERDOS					
Message rate					
1	43.0 μ s	86.5 μ s	175 μ s	187 μ s	0.33
10	6.40 μ s	87.0 μ s	188 μ s	215 μ s	0.35
100	33.0 μ s	88.5 μ s	190 μ s	627 μ s	0.41
1000	8.00 μ s	9.00 μ s	120 μ s	1.93 ms	1.99
10000	6.00 μ s	9.00 μ s	120 μ s	19.2 ms	15.14
100000	4.00 μ s	10.0 μ s	139 μ s	47.6 ms	16.72

TABLE I: Statistical figures corresponding to the values illustrated in 6a, including the Coefficient of Variation (C_V)

Throughput Tests: The goal of this test is to measure the E2E application throughput for a baseline pipeline. Fig.5b depicts the application tested that is composed by a source, injecting data, an operator forwarding data from its input to its output, and a sink printing each second the number of messages received. All the operators run on the same machine. The messages are injected by the source as fast as possible, and the payload size varies from 1 byte up to 16MB — matching the size of images sent by HD cameras [13].

Results: The results of the tests are illustrated in Fig. 6b, which depicts the median number of messages per second. Both solutions present a stable throughput. As these tests consist in sending data as fast as possible, the threads running the

operators are always scheduled by the OS, thus leveraging time locality and, therefore, increasing the throughput.

Moreover, results show that Zenoh-Flow outperforms ERDOS by more than one order of magnitude, and presents a more stable behaviour for bigger payloads. Such behaviour comes from the immutability of data at operators inputs, enabling zero-copy communications in links, while ERDOS finds itself copying data. For higher payloads, this hits the performances of ERDOS as it involves memory access, thus slowing down the process.

C. Resource Usage in a Robotic Use Case

The goal of this test is to verify that Zenoh-Flow is able to cover a real experimental robotic use case. The testbed is comprised of a ROBOTIS TurtleBot3, equipped by a RaspberryPI 3B and an OpenCR microcontroller board, a Linksys WRT3200ACM, and a Dell XPS 9750, equipped with Intel i7-8750H CPU, 16GB of RAM, 512GB SSD and running Ubuntu 20.04.3 LTS up-to-date at the time of the testing.

Description: The robotic application, illustrated in Fig.5c, consists of the teleoperation of the TurtleBot3 from the laptop, which moves in a straight line for about 2 meters. To do so, the keyboard operation is scripted so that the exact same sequence of commands are sent during the test. Finally, multiple devices are involved and communicate via an 802.11g wireless network. In these tests, we measure CPU, memory and network usage as well as Count Line Of Code (CLOC) to assess the complexity of each operator of the application.

Results: Table II summarizes the results of the test. Our proposed solution allows for smaller code-base, with an overall reduction of 83.9% and 61.8% compared to respectively ROS and ROS2. Furthermore, Zenoh-Flow allows reducing CPU usage by 74.7% and 43.8% and RAM usage by 89.2% and 83.4% on the TurtleBot3 respectively to ROS and ROS2. Leaving more resources for application’s business logic.

Framework	Lines of code			Resource usage							
	MOTORS	LIDAR	TELEOPERATION	CPU (%)		MEMORY (MB)		NETWORK (KB)			
				Robot	Laptop	Robot	Laptop	Sent		Received	
								Robot	Laptop	Robot	Laptop
ROS	4537	222	145	13.95	0.09	92	75	110	96	96	110
ROS2	1652	210	151	6.27	0.02	60	38	187	192	192	187
Zenoh-Flow	586	64	52	3.53	0.01	10	10	92	56	56	92

TABLE II: Comparison between ROS, ROS2 and Zenoh-Flow on the robotic teleoperation use-case. This table shows the overhead in both lines of codes and resource usage.

It also reduces significantly the data exchanged over the network (between 28.1% and 59.6%), thus leaving more bandwidth to the application. The difference on network usage comes from the underlying data plane technology, where Zenoh provides less overhead compared to ROS communication protocol and ROS2 DDS.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

With the advent of the Cloud-to-Thing continuum, as a paramount technology for upcoming 6G networks, IoT-based applications in e.g. Automotive and Robotics are growing in complexity. The need for completely decentralized and distributed components and all the inherent communication aspects are leading to a patchwork design which increases development times and costs. To this extent, in this work a novel data flow programming framework, named Zenoh-Flow, is introduced that provides unified set of abstractions, automated bin-packing and deployment, and other real-time functionalities key like deadlines and time-stamping. Such set of features are nowadays requirements of IoT-based applications in both Automotive and Robotics industries. Preliminary results show that our proposed solution outperforms existing and widely adopted state-of-the-art solutions. In particular, it showcases lower latency and higher throughput in synthetic benchmarks as well as less computing and networking overhead in a real-world robotic scenario.

As future work, the support for time-triggered computations is being considered, as an increment to today's event-trigger schema, as well as an integration with Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) for the data plane.

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